

More on the crab spider *Smodicinus coroniger* Simon, 1895 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The rare, crowned crab spider *Smodicinus coroniger* Simon, 1895, is an African endemic species that was described from Sierra Leone, West Africa, based on an immature specimen. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on live specimens with notes on their behaviour, conservation status and distribution in South Africa.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Thomisidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). *Smodicinus coroniger* Simon, 1895 was recognized by its modified carapace, which is highly elevated to form a crest (Fig. 1).

Smodicinus Simon, 1895 is monotypic and known only from Africa. The type-species *Smodicinus coroniger* was described from Sierra Leone, West Africa, based on immature specimens. A second species, *S. affinis*, from Zaïre, was added by Lessert (1943) based on a female. He stated that this species differs from *S. coroniger* in the shape of its crest. In a third paper, Jézéquel (1966) provided the first drawing of the male palp of *S. coroniger*. *Smodicinus coroniger* was the first time recorded from South Africa sampled from trees at Maasstroom in the Limpopo province.

The genus was revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) and specimens from six collections were examined. It was found the shape of the crest is variable. In *S. coroniger* the posterior pair of tubercles of the crest and genitalia resemble *S. affinis* and the species was recognized as a junior synonym of *S. coroniger*. In the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) several more specimens sampled from the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal were listed. In this paper more information is added on their morphology, behaviour, conservation status and distribution.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Requests were also made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Smodicinus coroniger Simon, 1895

Smodicinus coroniger Simon, 1895a: 433; 1895b: 992
Jézéquel, 1966: 625; Dippenaar-Schoeman 1980: 339;
Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 4.

Description: **Size:** TL females and males 3–6 mm. The carapace is pale brown, infused with yellow, sometimes with white markings on the edge. The carapace is modified, it is highly elevated to form a crest that is flattened above with six-pointed tubercles; two tubercles are pointed posteriorly and four laterally (Figs 1 & 3). Eyes: both eye rows recurved; situated on small tubercles; laterals larger than medians; posterior lateral eyes smallest, situated nearer to posterior lateral eyes than to each other; median ocular quadrangle broader than long with the posterior lateral eyes situated on the posterior side and the anterior lateral eyes situated anteriorly (Figs 1 & 2).

Figures 1–3. *Smodicinus coroniger* female. Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Figures 4–10. *Smodicinus coroniger*. 4-5. Female carapace dorsal view. 6. Female habitus dorsal view. 7. Female habitus ventral view. 8–9. Male palp. 10. Epigyne. Credits: 4, 6 & 7. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 5 & 10. Lessert (1943). 8-9. Jézéquel (1966).

Chelicerae anteriorly flattened, bearing on the edge small tubercles, each provided with a seta which is directed forwards (Fig. 1). Clypeus slightly sloping forwards, provided with two pairs of primary setae; lateral sides of clypeus with a pair of anterior-directed projections. Sternum and mouthparts yellowish-brown. Abdomen ovoid, blackish, mottled with white or with distinct white markings (Fig. 5); ventrally with two white spots mediolaterally (Fig. 6); spinnerets and epigastric area sometimes encircled with white. Legs I and II brown, banded with white; longer and stronger; rest only slightly longer than III and IV, the femora each provided with one strong dorsal seta; femur I armed with two small tubercles bearing a seta on each. Legs with a single spine on dorsal femur III and IV, otherwise spineless. Epigynum as wide as long, with a depression medially, divided longitudinally by an indistinct septum (Fig. 9). Palp with coiled retro lateral apophysis (Figs 8 & 9).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ivory Coast (Lamto), Sierra Leone, South Africa and Zaire.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.01, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87). **Limpopo:** Alldays (-22.67, 29.10); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.65, 29.04); Maasstroem (Farm Al te ver) (-22.75, 28.43); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Syferkuil (-23.85, 29.712).

iNaturalist : No records from South Africa listed.

LIFESTYLE

Smodicinus coroniger is free-living plant-dwellers. According to Lessert (1943) they are myrmecomorphic imitating the tree ant *Cataulacus erinaceus* Stitz. During surveys mainly in the Savanna Biome *S. coroniger* was sampled while beating trees (Foord *et al.*, 2011). In the Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009) it was sampled from *Burkea africana*. In the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) it was sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* and *V. xanthophloea* trees in the forests around the pans and Sand Forest. Males were sampled from November to March and females from October to January.

Figures 11–12. *Smodicinus coroniger* female. Credits: Brian Ashby

CONSERVATION STATUS

During SANSA surveys, the species have been sampled from three provinces and it is protected in the following reserves: Cwebe Nature Reserve; Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Mkuzi Game Reserve; Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve; Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa *et al.*, 2010) and Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009).

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